

Gender in Gig Economy: Evidence from Bibliometric Review and Content Analysis

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Abstract

Problem Definition: Gig economy is a new but emerging concept in the employment model. Like all the other employment models, there exists gender dynamics and inequality in Gig Economy. Therefore this study tries to bring out the major themes for the identification of various spectrums of Gender inequality

Methodology: SPAR 4 SLR methodology was used to screen the articles. A Bibliometric analysis using Vos Viewer and Content Analysis using Word stat was conducted on 54 papers

Results: The result of the Bibliometric and Content Analysis suggest that the association between Women and Gig Economy is an emerging but recent topic. Developed countries associate with themselves in research in this area. The keyword analysis done using Vosviewer and the content analysis done using Wordstat aligns with each other

Managerial Implication: The results of the study highlights that more studies must be carried out on Gender and Gig economy especially from the developing countries.

Keywords: Gig Economy, Gender, Inequality, VosViewer, Wordstat

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Introduction

Gender equality and paid work are important topics in the discourse on international development. It is believed that new digital technologies would provide marginalised individuals, especially women, with paid employment. Growing numbers of women are joining the workforce as a result of the platform economy, which is defined as labour that is digitally mediated through platforms and is marketed as a solution to gender inequity and poverty. Because of the dual load of reproductive and productive labour, women continue to face structural vulnerability in the labour market (Anwar, 2022). Globally, about 163 million workers—including over 64 million women—find paid employment through digital labour platforms. Since labour platforms break the traditional link between production and formal employment, it is stated that they represent “a technological revolution like no other” (James, 2024).

Gig Economy researchers are quite developing and are yet to be explored. Like any other traditional market, the gig labour market is also not free of any gender discrimination. In the light of this, it is essential to identify the state of researches carried out to explore the presence of women in gig economy. One of the research methods used to understand the status of the studies done in a particular area is Bibliometrics research.

In the present study a quantitative approach is carried out by using a bibliometrics analysis to find out the already existing research done on this area. The articles are downloaded from the Scopus website. For the purpose, Scientific Procedures and Rationales for Systematic Literature Reviews (SPAR-4-SLR) protocol is followed for the purpose of assembling, arranging and assessing the articles. 54 articles are finally selected for conducting the research. VosViewer is used for studying bibliometrics. Further a Qualitative Analysis was also conducted using Wordstat.

The paper is divided into following sections namely Methodology and data, Results and Discussion, Conclusions, Scope for future research.

Methodology and data

Methodology

For the bibliometric analysis, this study used both quantitative and qualitative methodologies (Donthu et al., 2021). (1) Trend and evolution analysis; (2) Keyword co-occurrence cartography analysis; (3) Citation analysis of bibliometric authors, organisations, and countries; (4) Citation analysis of bibliometric papers and sources; (5) Co-citation analysis of bibliometric references; and (6) Content Analysis were carried out. There were two main software programs used. WordStat was utilised for content analysis while VosViewer was employed for bibliometric analysis.

Data

The study employed the Scientific Procedures and Rationales for Systematic Literature Reviews (SPAR-4-SLR) protocol's updated review procedure, as per Paul and Criado's (2020) guidelines. Figure 1 presents the search strategy and the numerous techniques used to extract the data. Assembling, organising, and evaluating are the three phases of data retrieval and utilisation that the SPAR-4-SLR protocol recommends.

Assembling

This stage further has two sub-stages: identification and acquisition (Paul and Criado, 2020). The objective of the identification sub-stage was to explore studies which include the women and Gig Economy in their studies. The database used for the extraction of data was the Scopus database as it contains high quality journals compared to various other databases. The search syntax contains the terms "gig economy" and "women." On August 16, 2024, a search was conducted in Scopus, producing 92 documents. A number of additional refining procedures, including search time, subject area, source, and document type, were implemented during the acquisition substage. August 16, 2024, was the search date. "Social sciences," "business, management, and accounting," and "economics, econometrics, and finance" are among the topic areas covered. 54 papers in total were found through the search that will be taken into consideration for the study.

Arranging

The selected data without any further purification were exported to CSV Excel and uploaded to VOS viewer to conduct bibliometric analysis.

Assessing

Again, there are two sub-stages inside the assessment stage: reporting and evaluation. In order to accomplish the first three research objectives, bibliometric analysis and science mapping were used to analyse 54 papers during the evaluation process. Using VOSviewer, bibliometric analysis was carried out to identify the principal groupings of excellent research that explored the relationship between women and the gig economy and met the first research goal. Specifically, VOSviewer's "keyword co-occurrence cartography" tool was used to identify the main themes related to the research field. To fulfil the second study goal, further bibliometric and science mapping analyses were carried out, including "authors', organisations', and countries' citation analysis, papers' and sources' citation analysis, and references' co-citation analysis." In addition, content analysis was done in order to accomplish the third research goal, investigate the relationship between women and the gig economy, and determine recommendations for additional study. This research's reporting substage displays the findings in the form of figures

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and is consistent with earlier systematic literature reviews (Donthu et al., 2021; Goodell et al., 2023; Lim and Kumar, 2024; Mukherjee et al., 2022).

Figure 1: SPAR SLR

Results and Discussion

Bibliometric, and content analysis

The number of publications in association to women and Gig Economy in the recent years is shown in Figure 2. The first publication in association with women and Gig Economy was made in the year 2018. From there on there is a steep increase in the number of publications in the following years. There is also a dip in the publications in 2020. An increase can be further seen and again the number of publications have hit a downward trend in the year 2023. The increase in the number of publications can be attributed to the demanding importance of sustainable development goal 5 which stands for the equality of women in workplaces.

Figure 2: Publication Trend

Bibliometric analyses

The 54 articles that make up this study are compiled in this section. The following bibliometric analyses were carried out: (1) “trend and evolution analyses in Gender and Gig Economy research”; (2) “co-occurrence of all keywords in cartography analysis”; (3) “bibliometric citation analyses of authors, organisations, and countries”; (4) “bibliometric citation analyses of papers and sources”; and (5) “co-citation analysis of bibliometric references”.

Most frequent research topics

To conceptualise the rise and development of the Women-Gig Economy linkage analysis in articles published in Scopus journals, co-occurrence analysis was performed on all the keywords. In accordance with Khan et al. (2022), a minimum of two was maintained as the threshold for the co-occurrence of a certain term in order to ensure the analysis’s significance. Out of 286 words, this produced 51. Five main clusters are displayed in Figure 3 of the results: labour market, China, digital platforms, gender, and platform economy. The recurrent themes in these publications undermine the need for studies on the relationship between women and the gig economy as an opposition to the introduction of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Figure 3 demonstrates the intersectional nature of gig economy research, specifically how gender influences experiences within this economic paradigm. The prominence of keywords such as “COVID-19” and “platformisation” indicates that these are new areas of study in the context of gig labour and gender. The inclusion of individual countries such as “China” and “India” may suggest regional research or comparative analyses within a larger discourse.

Figure 3: Keyword Analysis

Table 1 : Table showing the Keyword Occurrences

Key words	Occurrences
Gig Economy	33
Gender	17
Employment	8
Platform Economy	6
Gender Discrimination	5
Covid-19	4
Gender Role	4
Gender Disparity	3
Female	2

Authorship Analysis

Figure 4 demonstrates that there are 54 total authors, with each author publishing only one document. There is no connection strength between them. The author “Kwan H.” is highly featured in the network, implying that he is a key person in this study group, possibly working closely with other scholars. The visualisation depicts several clusters, each representing a distinct research group or theme area. “Chen Y.,” “Anwar M.A.,” and “Zhang Q.,” are key figures in their respective clusters.

Figure 4: Authorship Analysis

Table 2 : Table showing Co authorship analysis

List of Authors	Citations
Churchill B.; Craig L.	81
Cook C.; Diamond R.; Hall J.V.; List J.A.; Oyer P.	29
Komaraju S.A.; Arora P.; Raman U.	10
Kwan H. (2 Documents)	13

Country Analysis

Figure 5 illustrates a list of nations that have published articles on Women in the Gig Economy. Gig economy publications involve a total of eight countries. The majority of these publications have come from the United States and the United Kingdom, followed by Ireland. The United States, United Kingdom, and Ireland form a strongly connected cluster, indicating that researchers in these nations commonly communicate. This cluster is central to the network, indicating its significance in the research field. Countries like Malaysia and Mexico appear on the periphery with few or no observable linkages, implying that these countries may be under-represented in international collaborations or focus primarily on regional research.

Figure5: Country Analysis

Table 3: Table showing Country analysis

Country	Documents	Citations
Australia	4	101
Germany	4	143
Hong Kong	4	17
India	6	55
Spain	4	12
United Kingdom	9	53
United States	12	203

Organisation Analysis

Figure 6 depicts the major organisations that are involved in the publication of Women in the Gig Economy. The top four institutions conducting research on the gig economy and women are the University of Southern California, Northwestern University, the University of Melbourne, and Humboldt University in Berlin.

Table 4 : Table showing Organisation analysis

Organization	Documents	Citations
Humboldt University Berlin, Germany	1	29
Northwestern University United States	1	0
University Of Melbourne Graduate School Of Education, Australia	1	2
University Of Southern California, Los Angeles, Ca, United States	1	6

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Figure 6: Organisation Analysis

Most cited papers

An study of the documents' citations was done. This is in line with the requirement of at least two citations for each work. Out of 54 papers, this produced 42. As important writers or groups in the network, Churchill B., Craig L., Cook C., Diamond R., Hall J.V., Webster N.A., and Zhang Q. stand out. The network displays several research communities, each represented by a few central nodes that serve as bridges and indicate that the authors or articles in question have a wider influence on a variety of subfields.

Figure 7: Most cited papers

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Table 5 : Table showing most cited papers

Document	Citations
Webster N.A.; Zhang Q. (2020)	9
Churchill B.; Craig L. (2019)	40
Cook C.; Diamond R.; Hall J.V.; List J.A.; Oyer P. (2021)	2

Most co cited Reference Papers

The top 20 co-cited references from articles on women and the gig economy that were published in Scopus journals are shown in this section. This translates to a minimum of two citation threshold, which produced 78 references out of 2596. Given that this study topic is relatively new—the first publication in this field was published in 2018—the analysis reveals that the majority of the top co-cited reference articles also suggest that the maximum number of citations for these publications is two. Nine references are quoted the most, followed by five and four. Journal articles provide the vast majority of the references. Churchill B., Craig L. (Gender), Graham M., Hjorth I., and Lehdonvirta V. are significant references in this field of study that have an effect on a number of research issues. With some references connecting these themes, the network exposes distinct study themes, including labour practices, gig economy, and gender studies. As illustrated in Figure 8, the visualisation demonstrates how some works serve as links between various research communities, indicating their broad applicability or interdisciplinary significance.

Table 6: Table showing Most Cited References

Cited Reference	Citations	Total Link Strength
Betti E., Historicizing Precarious Work: Forty Years Of Research In The Social Sciences And Humanities, <i>International Review Of Social History</i> , 63, 2, Pp. 273-319, (2018)	3	9
Churchill B., Craig L., Gender In The Gig Economy: Men And Women Using Digital Platforms To Secure Work In Australia, <i>Journal Of Sociology</i> , 55, 4, Pp. 741-761, (2019)	9	20
Gerber C., Gender And Precarity In Platform Work: Old Inequalities In The New World Of Work, <i>New Technology, Work And Employment</i> , 37, 2, Pp. 206-230, (2022)	3	10
Graham M., Hjorth I., Lehdonvirta V., Digital Labour And Development: Impacts Of Global Digital Labour Platforms And The Gig Economy On Worker Livelihoods, <i>Transfer: European</i>		

Review Of Labour And Research, 23, 2, Pp. 135-162, (2017)	5	11
Hunt A., Samman E., (2019)	2	14
Kaihko I., Conflict Chatnography: Instant Messaging Apps, Social Media And Conflict Ethnography In Ukraine, Ethnography, 21, 1, Pp. 71-91, (2020)	2	11
Lehdonvirta V., Flexibility In The Gig Economy: Managing Time On Three Online Piecework Platforms, New Technology, Work And Employment, 33, 1, Pp. 13-29, (2018)	4	7
Ravenelle A.J., Hustle And Gig: Struggling And Surviving In The Sharing Economy, (2019)	3	11
Van Doorn N., Platform Labor: On The Gendered And Racialized Exploitation Of Low-Income Service Work In The 'On-Demand' Economy, Information, Communication & Society, 20, 6, Pp. 898-914, (2017)	4	5
Wood A.J., Graham M., Lehdonvirta V., Hjorth I., Good Gig, Bad Gig: Autonomy And Algorithmic Control In The Global Gig Economy, Work, Employment And Society, 33, 1, Pp. 56-75, (2019)	5	14

Figure 8: Co cited References papers

Most co cited References Author

The majority of reference authors' citation analyses are shown in this section. Two citations is the minimum threshold for an author, so 24 out of 3469 authors meet this requirement.

Figure 9 illustrates the important authors and their links through co-citations, highlighting the complexity of the study area. It is suggested that authors such as Graham M., Craig L., and Dunn M. are key players in their research communities by the essential roles they play in their particular clusters. The interdependence of research themes within this network and multidisciplinary influences are indicated by the links between clusters.

Figure 9: Co cited references Authors

Table 7: Table showing Most Co-cited References Author

Author	Citations	Total Link Strength
Graham M.	44	172
Hjorth I.	22	126
Lehdonvirta V.	41	184
Schieman S.	13	103
Wang S.	16	85

Content Analysis

Along with the bibliometric analysis, a qualitative content analysis was conducted using WordStat, A word cloud was created along with a Radar chart which aligned with the results of the bibliometric analysis. The major themes derived were, Gender, Gig , Digital, Employment, Labour, Economy.

The radar chart in Figure 10 covers the years 2018 through 2024, with a single axis for each year. Every category is represented by a coloured hexagon that displays its frequency for every year. It appears that categories like GENDER (green) and DIGITAL (purple) have gained more significance recently (2023 and 2024), suggesting an increase in conversations or mentions. The relative frequency for that year is indicated by the size and form of the polygons for each category. In 2024, for instance, a category will have a higher frequency if its polygon is large. As the years go by, there appears to be an increase in frequency for several categories, especially starting in 2022.

The polygons' overlapping areas imply that some subjects may have been discussed concurrently and at a comparable frequency in particular years. For example, there is a large overlap between the GENDER (green) and ECONOMY (pink) polygons, indicating that during specific times periods, both were discussed frequently together.

The United States, the United Kingdom, digital platforms, the platform economy, gig work, and the labour market are among the important terms displayed in Figure 11. These terms imply an emphasis on geographic areas and the infrastructure that facilitates gig employment. Indicating the social, psychological, and forward-looking elements of the gig economy, the Department of Sociology, Mental Health, Gender Discrimination, and Future of Work are also included.

Figure 10: Radar chart of major themes

Figure 11: Word cloud of major Keywords

Conclusion

Gender dynamics and Inequality plays a major role in the labour market irrespective of the form of market. Gig Economy being a developing and growing employment model is also

no exception. The flexible and autonomous nature of the work model attracts more people to join the gig economy. The pressure of doing both paid and unpaid work remains as a great challenge for the women workers to join the gig economy. Studies must be developed in this area to explore the association of women and gig economy. The findings of the bibliometric study reveal that gender is a key topic of discussion. Most of the studies are concentrated in United States and United Kingdom and they also have a good association between them. There are only very few authors who are the central characters in the research publication in this area and they are the key seminal paper publishers. Overall the study shows that, though there is a rise in the number of publications in association to Gender and Gig Economy, more studies must be published in the area especially from the developing countries

Scope for further research

Further research can be done on different measures such as skills, challenges etc. Also a Systematic Literature Review can be done on inequality and the state of representation of women in Gig Economy.

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मृदंग के संगीत पर जीवन के अभिनव राग का आख्यान : रसप्रिया

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एमिटी लॉ स्कूल, एमिटी यूनिवर्सिटी उत्तर प्रदेश

सार संक्षेप

‘फणीश्वर नाथ रेणु’ की ख्याति हिन्दी के आंचलिक कथाकार के रूप में है। रेणु के कथा साहित्य में लोक जीवन सरसता और सहजता सर्वत्र देखने को मिलती है। मैला आँचल इनके द्वारा रचित बहुचर्चित आंचलिक उपन्यास है, जिसमें कथाकार ने अंचल को नायक बनाकर अपने कथा के तानबाने की संश्लिष्ट बुनावट हमारे समक्ष प्रस्तुत किया है। मैला आँचल के साथ ही साथ ‘तीसरी कसम’ उर्फ ‘मारे गये गुल्फाम’ इनकी चर्चित कहानी है। इन दोनों कृतियों पर फिल्में भी बन चुकी हैं और इसके आधार पर इन्हें ख्याति भी खूब मिली। इसके अलावा इनके कथा-साहित्य में लोक का चटक रंग और राग देखने को मिलता है। लोक के अभिनव राग की दृष्टि से आपकी रसप्रिया कहानी अपने आप में विशिष्ट है, इस कहानी की मूल विषय-वस्तु तो मिरदंगिया और रामपतिया की प्रेमकथा है लेकिन कहानीकार ने इसके माध्यम से लोक जीवन के गीत-संगीत की सुदृढ़ परम्परा को हमारे समक्ष प्रस्तुत कर मिथिलानंचल के परिवेश को जीवन्त कर दिया है। लोक गायन, वादन और नर्तन की परम्परा के साथ जीवन में उसकी उपयोगिता के अंकन की दृष्टि से यह कहानी महत्वपूर्ण है।

संगीत हमारे मनोतंत्रियों को सुलझाता है और हमें मानसिक सुकून प्रदान करता है। ‘विद्यापति’ के पदों को गाते हुए मोहना, मिरदंगिया और लोक का लीन हो जाना एक मनोदशा है, जिसे गूंगे के गुड के सामना महसूस किया जा सकता है। इस कहानी का आस्वादन करते हुए हमारे